

NDAC/LO/035

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Intermediary quantities for FAST/NDAC intercomparison

by L Lindegren

0. Introduction

This note is a first iteration towards a definition of astrometric quantities suitable for intercomparison between the DRC. The consortia will have to agree on the exact definition of a small number of parameters, to which they can each apply their own estimation techniques. Ideally, these parameters should be "physically tangible" rather than mathematical abstractions. In reality it will be found, however, that such parameters can only be relevant in the framework of adopted mathematical models. A prerequisite for meaningful comparisons is therefore, that the consortia agree at least on the basic modelisation of the observation process. Given the complexity and non-uniqueness of these models, it is not obvious that a comparison is at all possible.

Fortunately it appears that FAST and NDAC think in terms of fairly similar processing schemes, which can be represented very broadly as follows:

<u>process</u>	<u>comparable parameters</u>
1. SM data processing	- transit times
2. Attitude reconstitution	- telescope pointing angles
3. IDT harmonic analysis and/or location estimation	- signal parameters and/or grid coordinates
4. Great circle (set) solution	- abscissae and/or angles between stars
5. Celestial sphere reconstitution	- astrometric parameters

Below I attempt to describe as precisely as possible the main parameters to be estimated by NDAC and indicate possible transformations to other quantities more suitable for comparison.

1. SM data processing

The main astrometric result of the SM data processing is the group transit time. The term "group" here refers to the assembly of four parallel slits: the vertical group and the chevron group. The group transit time is the unweighted mean of the four single-slit transit times, i.e. the instants when the star image is centred on a slit. The centrality criterion (at a slit) is a matter of convention and is in practice set by the origin of the adopted "single slit response function". (In view of image asymmetry, especially at the chevron slits, the definition of origin is non-trivial; I propose to use the intensity median.)

The transit times must be given on the "internal" time scale defined by the on-board clock; this is necessary since the absolute calibration of that scale (datation) is only accurate to about 1 ms (0.17 as). Furthermore, it will be necessary to agree on the assignment of internal time to the photometric samples (e.g. referring to the beginning, middle, or end of the sample?).

2. Attitude reconstitution

The attitude reconstitution determines the celestial orientation of the three telescope axes $\underline{x}$, $\underline{y}$, $\underline{z}$ (or, equivalently, of the two viewing directions $\underline{p}$ and $\underline{f}$: $\underline{p} = \underline{x} \cos \frac{1}{2}\gamma + \underline{y} \sin \frac{1}{2}\gamma$, $\underline{f} = \underline{x} \cos \frac{1}{2}\gamma - \underline{y} \sin \frac{1}{2}\gamma$, where γ is an agreed-upon nominal value for the basic angle). This can be expressed in different ways, e.g. by means of heliotropic attitude angles (Lindgren, 1984 April 17: The Nominal HIPPARCOS Scanning Law). A more direct way, perhaps better suitable for comparisons, would be to give the celestial coordinates of two axes: $\alpha_z(t)$, $\delta_z(t)$, $\alpha_x(t)$, $\delta_x(t)$. The argument is again the internal time discussed above; the celestial coordinate system is that defined by the Input Catalogue (e.g. formally the mean equatorial J2000.0 system as given by FK5). The redundancy (due to the constraint $\underline{x}'\underline{z} = 0$) obtained by giving four orientation angles rather than the minimum number may be a useful checkpoint against the most trivial interpretation errors.

The only real problem in the definition of attitude angles comes from the derivation of the field centre corresponding to the viewing directions, i.e. the origin of field angles η , ζ . This is the subject of a recent note (Lindgren, 1984 April 30: Definition of field angles), to which the reader is referred.

3. IDT harmonic analysis and location estimator

The processing of IDT data within NDAC relies strongly on the concept of a continuous "grid coordinate" G , such that $G = \text{integer}$ (= slit number) when the star image is centred on a slit. Centrality is defined by the maximum of the first harmonic for a point object; the photon counts are consequently supposed to be by a Poisson process with intensity

$$E(N_\ell) = B + A[1 + M_1 \cos(2\pi G_\ell) + M_2 \cos(4\pi G_\ell - v_2)] \quad (1)$$

where G_ℓ is the grid coordinate of the star at the (internal) time of the ℓ :th IDT sample (t_ℓ). B , A , M_1 , M_2 , and v_2 are supposed to be slowly varying functions of time (or rather position in field), i.e. with no appreciable power at the modulation frequencies. The grid coordinate can be written as function of field angles (η , ζ) in the form

$$G(\eta, \zeta) = \bar{G}(\eta, \zeta; f, B-V, t) + d(\eta, \zeta) \quad (2)$$

The first term is the large-scale distortion, representable by polynomials or similar functions depending on a small number of parameters, which in turn may depend on the field ($f = \pm 1$ for p/f), object colour, and time; the second term is the small-scale distortion represented by a matrix of scanfield parameters or similar. The separation of d from $\bar{G}$ can be made unique by means of suitable conditions of orthogonality.

3.1. Harmonic analysis

NDAC will estimate, for each frame (k) and each object (i) observed in that frame, the 5-vector $\underline{\beta}$ in

$$E(N_\ell) = \beta_1 + \beta_2 [\cos(\beta_3 + \epsilon_\ell) + \beta_4 \cos(2\beta_3 + 2\epsilon_\ell) + \beta_5 \sin(2\beta_3 + 2\epsilon_\ell)] \quad (3)$$

assuming it to be constant over the frame. ϵ_ℓ is the modulation phase of the first harmonic at time t_ℓ relative to the "smoothed" phase at frame midtime (t_k):

$$\epsilon_\ell = 2\pi \left[G[\tilde{\eta}(t_\ell), \tilde{\zeta}(t_\ell)] - \bar{G}[\tilde{\eta}(t_k), \tilde{\zeta}(t_k)] \right] \quad (4)$$

$\tilde{\eta}$, $\tilde{\zeta}$ denote field angles computed from current (inexact) astrometric and attitude data. β_3 is consequently the phase of the first harmonic at frame midtime, corrected for small-scale distortion:

$$\beta_3 = 2\pi\bar{G}_k \quad (5)$$

while the phase of the second harmonic is $\beta_3 - \frac{1}{2}\text{ATAN2}(\beta_5, \beta_4)$. Simultaneously with $\underline{\beta}$ we estimate its variance-covariance matrix $\underline{C}_\beta$, but not the covariance of the different stars in the frame.

The phase estimates are clearly ambiguous as to any whole number of rotations, as is $\bar{G}_k$ to its integer part. The ambiguity is provisionally settled at this stage by adopting the grid coordinate nearest to the a priori smoothed value, $\bar{G}[\tilde{\eta}(t_k), \tilde{\zeta}(t_k)]$.

3.2. Location estimation

The purpose of the location estimation is to obtain the best estimate of $\bar{G}_k$ using also the calibration values for M_1 , M_2 , and v_2 available at that time. It is now necessary to distinguish between single and multiple stars (or rather the stars which at this stage are believed to be single and multiple).

For single stars we have by virtue of (1) the following theoretical relations between $\underline{\beta}$ and the calibration parameters:

$$\beta_4 = (M_2/M_1) \cos v_2 \quad (6a)$$

$$\beta_5 = (M_2/M_1) \sin v_2 \quad (6b)$$

The location estimation can thus be seen as the simultaneous processing of the observation equations (3) with the calibration relations (6), given the a priori uncertainty of the latter. [In the limiting case when (6) is much better known than can be determined from (3) in a single frame, the calibration acts as a constraint, diminishing the number of free parameters in (3) to three, viz. $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$.]

For multiple stars the situation is much more complex. Remember, however, that the purpose is still to estimate the phase of the first harmonic, and nothing else. If there is no additional information on the multiple system, e.g. the relative position and intensity of components, the best estimate of $\bar{G}_k$ is simply that provided by the harmonic analysis, eqn (5).

4. Great circle solution

Batches of data (called "sets") covering some 6-12 h of observation will be reduced almost independently of each other; only the calibration of $(M_2/M_1) \cos v_2$ and $(M_2/M_1) \sin v_2$ versus field angles and colour will be based on a longer observation interval (perhaps a week). For each set we define a Reference Great Circle (RGC) by specifying the pole (α_r, δ_r) . The purpose of the set solution is to estimate the mean abscissa of each star, i.e. the angle (as viewed from the RGC pole) from the "ascending node" $(\alpha_r + \frac{1}{2}, 0)$ to the coordinate direction of the star at some specified mean time of observation. This latter time is chosen differently for each star, e.g. as the arithmetic mean of all frame midtimes in the set at which the star was observed; this reference time is not allowed to change in the course of the set solution, even if some frames are deleted or down-weighted. The coordinate direction to the star, i.e., excluding aberration and gravitational deflexion, must be used in this definition since the two effects may have non-linear variations in the course of a set. The abscissa origin is at this stage of course only defined to the accuracy permitted by the Input Catalogue ($\sim 10 - 50$ mas)

For comparison purposes it is acceptable to make a small number of special set solutions outside the regular processing schedule. The data that need to be specified are: set interval (first, last frame), RGC pole, reference time (individually for the stars or common to the whole set), and calibration data to be used.

As an alternative, it is perhaps easier to ask specific questions such as: "Given the data set from frame X to Y, what is the estimated angle at time t between objects i_1 and i_2 ?" Here, i_1 and i_2 should preferably be of the order of 90° apart on the sky. (The term "angle" must be clearly defined, e.g. the angle between the coordinate directions.)

5. Celestial sphere reconstitution

The comparison of astrometric parameters for single stars is straightforward, but for multiple stars we need to agree on the physical model applicable to each object before comparison is possible.